

EULISH - Modern lingua franca

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Summary: Creating a systematized version of English for citizens of the European Union could help foster clearer, more efficient communication, particularly in multilingual and multinational contexts. By reducing synonyms, simplifying grammar, and standardizing vocabulary, English could become a more accessible and neutral language for the diverse population of the European Union. A linguistic authority is needed and the European Union could adopt these measures to implement a common language on the territory of the EU Member States, and a citizens' initiative would be a good omen.

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Having a common language rooted in English

Imagine that having a common language rooted in English across all European peoples could bring several advantages like:

1. **Ease of Communication** : It would facilitate seamless communication across borders, promoting better understanding, cooperation, and efficiency in various sectors like trade, diplomacy, and education.
2. **Cultural Exchange** : A shared language could enhance cultural exchange and mutual appreciation of diverse European cultures, fostering a sense of unity amidst diversity.
3. **Economic Benefits** : It could potentially lower barriers to trade and investment by reducing language-related costs and barriers to entry, thereby boosting economic integration and growth.
4. **Political Cohesion** : Common language can aid in political cooperation and decision-making within the European Union and other international forums, streamlining processes and enhancing effectiveness.
5. **Educational Opportunities** : A common language could simplify educational exchanges and collaboration among European universities, researchers, and students, enhancing academic opportunities and innovation.

Overall, while preserving linguistic diversity is important, a common language rooted in English could enhance unity, cooperation, and prosperity across Europe.

About the English language in a nutshell

The English language is a West Germanic language that originated in early medieval England and has become a global lingua franca. It is the most widely spoken language worldwide, both by native speakers and as a second language. Here are some key points about English:

English developed from the languages spoken by the Anglo-Saxons in Britain. Its roots can be traced back to Old English, heavily influenced by Norse due to Viking invasions, and later by Norman French after the Norman Conquest of 1066.

English has evolved significantly over the centuries:

- Old English (c. 450-1150) : Closely related to Old German and Norse languages.
- Middle English (1150-1500) : Influenced by Norman French, resulting in many borrowed words.
- Modern English (1500-present) : Shaped by the Renaissance, colonization, and scientific advancements.

English expanded globally through the British Empire in the 16th-20th centuries and later became the dominant language of international business, science, technology, and entertainment, especially with the rise of the United States.

English has many regional dialects and varieties, such as British, American, Australian, and Indian English, each with its own distinct pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary.

English grammar is relatively simple compared to some other languages. For example, it has no gender for nouns (except for personal pronouns), no case system, and limited inflection for verbs (compared to languages like Spanish or Russian).

English has an extremely large and varied vocabulary, thanks to its history of borrowing from many languages. Words from Latin, French, Germanic, Greek, and more are part of everyday use.

English is the official or dominant language in many countries and international organizations, making it essential for global communication, education, and business.

In short, English is a dynamic, evolving language with deep historical roots and a global influence that continues to grow.

Many words have been taken from Latin, French, German or other languages.

Multiple synonyms in English

The problem of multiple synonyms in English arises from the language's rich and complex history of borrowing words from different languages, resulting in many words that have similar or identical meanings. While this gives English a vast and nuanced vocabulary, it also presents challenges:

1. Ambiguity in Word Choice :

- Synonyms often carry subtle differences in tone, formality, or context, which can lead to confusion for both native speakers and learners of the language. For example, "happy," "joyful," and "elated" all refer to positive emotions, but they differ in intensity and usage.

- Happy : General contentment or pleasure.

- Joyful : Stronger, more exuberant happiness.

- Elated : Intense, elevated happiness, often linked to a specific event or achievement.

- Choosing the "wrong" synonym may change the nuance of a sentence, making it more or less formal, or conveying a slightly different meaning.

2. Redundancy :

- The large number of synonyms can lead to redundancy, where two or more words with essentially the same meaning are used interchangeably without adding any value. This can make writing verbose or unnecessarily complex.

- For instance, "big," "large," "huge," and "gigantic" all express size, but some might be redundant in certain contexts unless a specific nuance is needed.

3. Difficulty for Learners :

- English learners face the challenge of understanding when and how to use each synonym appropriately. Often, words that seem interchangeable are used in different contexts or registers (formal vs. informal language).

- For instance, "begin" and "commence" mean the same thing, but "commence" is more formal, and using it in casual speech might sound awkward.

4. Influence of Etymology :

- English synonyms often originate from different linguistic roots. For example:

- Anglo-Saxon roots : Words like "help" and "buy" are usually shorter and more direct.

- Latin or French roots : Words like "assist" (from Latin *assistere*) and "purchase" (from French *purchaser*) often sound more formal and are used in more official or academic contexts.

- The choice between these synonyms can signal social class, education level, or formality. This layering of synonyms can make English feel inconsistent, adding to the challenge.

5. Context-Dependent Meaning :

- Even when words are technically synonyms, their usage can vary greatly depending on context. For example, "house" and "home" are synonyms, but "home" carries a more personal, emotional connotation, while "house" refers to the physical building.

- Words like "ask" and "inquire" both mean to seek information, but "inquire" is more formal and might be reserved for professional or written communication.

6. Connotations and Cultural Differences :

- Many synonyms carry connotations that may not be obvious. For example, "slim" and "skinny" both describe someone who is thin, but "slim" is usually a compliment, while "skinny" can imply being too thin in an unhealthy or unattractive way.

- These subtle distinctions can vary by region or culture, making synonym choice even more complicated across English-speaking countries.

7. Word History and Precision :

- Synonyms often reflect the evolution of a word's meaning over time. For example, "prevent" and "preclude" both imply stopping something, but "preclude" is more specific and legalistic. Understanding the history behind each synonym can add precision but also complexity to communication.

The abundance of synonyms in English can make the language richer and more expressive, but it also complicates communication by introducing ambiguity, redundancy, and potential for miscommunication. This requires speakers and writers to carefully consider not just the literal meaning of words, but also their connotations, tone, and context.

Envisioning a systematized version of the English language

Envisioning a systematized version of the English language for greater clarity and use across the European Union (EU) involves simplifying the language by removing unnecessary synonyms and establishing more precise language rules. This idea could help eliminate ambiguity, making English a clearer and more standardized tool for communication among EU member states.

Key Features of a Simplified, Systematized English for the EU:

1. Elimination of Redundant Synonyms :

- Selection of a Single Word for Each Meaning : To reduce confusion, one word could be chosen as the standard for a particular concept, while others with similar meanings would be phased out in official contexts. For example:

- Choose either "start" or "begin," not both.

- Use "buy" instead of "purchase" to simplify formal and casual communication.

- This would streamline communication and ensure that non-native speakers do not have to differentiate between similar words in various contexts.

2. Clear and Consistent Grammar Rules :

- Regularization of Irregular Verbs : Many irregular verbs in English, like "go/went" or "write/wrote," could be regularized to follow consistent patterns, making conjugation easier. For instance, all past tense verbs could end in "-ed" (e.g., "goed" instead of "went").

- Simplification of Pronouns and Articles : Pronouns and articles (like "a" and "the") could be streamlined. For example, adopting one neutral pronoun (such as "they" for both singular and plural) and reducing complexity in articles could make the language easier to learn and use.

3. Consistent Use of Words Across Contexts :

- In the current version of English, certain words change meaning depending on the context (e.g., "set" can mean multiple things). A systematized version would ensure each word has only one clear meaning, reducing the potential for confusion.

- Specialized terminology (e.g., in legal, business, or scientific contexts) could still exist, but basic communication would focus on clear, unambiguous terms.

4. Standardized Vocabulary Across the EU :

- Use of Internationally Recognizable Terms : For effective communication across member states, the vocabulary could focus on words that have clear, universally recognized meanings and are easier for non-native speakers to grasp.

- Borrowing Terms from Other Languages : Some key terms from other languages within the EU could be incorporated into the systematized English, reflecting the cultural diversity of Europe while maintaining clarity and precision.

5. Neutral Tone and Avoidance of Cultural Bias :

- By removing certain words or phrases that have strong connotations in specific English-speaking countries (e.g., British or American idioms), the language would be made more neutral and suitable for use across different cultural contexts.

- This approach would help English serve as a truly neutral "lingua franca" for the EU, avoiding favoritism toward any particular regional version of the language.

6. Standardization of Spelling and Pronunciation :

- Unified Spelling Rules : Currently, there are spelling differences between British and American English (e.g., "colour" vs. "color"). A standardized version of English would adopt one consistent spelling for all EU communications.

- Phonetic Spelling : Spelling could be simplified to reflect pronunciation more accurately, reducing the irregularities that make English difficult for non-native speakers. For instance, words like "though" could be spelled "tho" to align with pronunciation.

7. Focus on Clarity and Simplicity in Legal and Administrative Language :

- In legal and official EU documents, English would be simplified to ensure clarity for all speakers. Overly complex legalese or jargon would be minimized to make laws and regulations easier to understand across member states.

Benefits for the EU:

- Improved Multinational Communication : A simplified, standardized version of English would enable smoother communication between member states, facilitating cooperation, trade, and diplomacy.
- Easier for Non-Native Speakers : By removing synonyms and simplifying grammar and vocabulary, learning and using English would become easier for millions of non-native speakers within the EU.
- Cultural Neutrality : This approach would ensure that no single English-speaking country (e.g., the UK or the US) dominates the language, making it a truly neutral medium for the EU's diverse population.

Challenges:

- Resistance from Native Speakers : Native English speakers may resist changes to grammar, vocabulary, or spelling that simplify the language for non-native speakers.
- Complexity of Implementation : It would be a significant effort to enforce and spread a new, standardized version of English across multiple institutions, educational systems, and media in the EU.
- Cultural Loss : Synonyms and idiomatic expressions add richness and depth to a language, and removing them could be seen as diminishing the expressiveness of English.

In summary, creating a systematized version of English for citizens of the European Union could help foster clearer, more efficient communication, particularly in multilingual and multinational contexts. By reducing synonyms, simplifying grammar, and standardizing vocabulary, English could become a more accessible and neutral language for the diverse population of the European Union.

The language regulators

A language authority is an official or semi-official organization responsible for regulating or standardizing a language, often by developing grammar rules, spelling standards, and dictionaries. These authorities aim to maintain linguistic consistency and serve as references for proper usage, ensuring that a language evolves in a structured way. Examples of language authorities for other languages include:

- Académie Française for French
- Real Academia Española for Spanish
- Institut für Deutsche Sprache for German

Unlike many other languages, English does not have a central, official language authority. This is due to several reasons:

1. Historical and Geographical Spread : English is spoken as a first language in many countries (the UK, the US, Canada, Australia, etc.), each with its own linguistic norms and traditions.
2. Global Nature : English serves as a global lingua franca, used by people worldwide, making it difficult to regulate by a single body.

Instead of a single regulating authority, English relies on a combination of major institutions, dictionaries, and style guides. These serve as unofficial authorities on proper English usage. Examples include:

- Oxford University Press (OUP) : Publishers of the Oxford English Dictionary (OED), which is considered one of the most authoritative dictionaries of the English language.
- Merriam-Webster : An American dictionary known for its influence on American English usage.
- Chicago Manual of Style and Associated Press (AP) Stylebook : Style guides widely used in journalism and publishing.
- Cambridge University Press : Known for its dictionary and educational materials on British English.

These organizations influence the evolution and usage of English but do not impose rules as an official regulatory body would. Therefore, English is unique in that it evolves organically, with these references guiding rather than mandating language use.

I believe that for Eulish, a regulator is needed if such language is to be accepted. A language authority plays a crucial role in ensuring the stability, clarity, and effective communication within a language community. Here are several reasons why having a language authority can be considered necessary:

1. Standardization and Consistency

A language authority ensures consistent rules for grammar, spelling, and pronunciation across different regions and dialects. This standardization is important for:

- Education : Students need a clear and uniform framework to learn a language correctly.
- Publishing : Authors, journalists, and translators require common standards for clarity and coherence.
- Media : Ensuring uniform language usage in the press, online platforms, and official publications helps in preventing miscommunication.

Without standardization, communication could become fragmented, with regional differences creating confusion.

2. Preservation of Language

Language authorities often take on the role of preserving the purity of a language . This means safeguarding a language from:

- Unregulated Borrowings : Excessive borrowing from other languages could dilute the core identity of the language.
- Degeneration : Over time, without regulation, language can lose its original structure and richness, as unapproved colloquialisms or slang dominate communication.

Authorities ensure that a balance is maintained between evolving language usage and preserving its historical and cultural heritage.

3. Cultural Identity and Unity

Language is deeply tied to a community's cultural identity . A language authority helps preserve not only the linguistic framework but also the cultural elements embedded within it. When a standard language is promoted:

- It fosters national unity and identity, especially in multilingual societies (e.g., France's Académie Française works to preserve the French language against external influences).
- It helps reduce the divergence of dialects , ensuring that speakers of different dialects can communicate effectively and feel part of the same linguistic community.

4. Regulating Language Evolution

Language naturally evolves, but without a central regulating body, it can evolve too quickly or in a chaotic manner. An authority:

- Provides guidance on language changes , helping incorporate new words and expressions while maintaining a coherent system.
- Decides which neologisms (newly coined words) become part of the official lexicon, ensuring that language evolves in a structured way.
- Helps modernize the language without losing its essence, ensuring it remains relevant and adaptable to societal, scientific, and technological advancements.

5. Resolving Disputes and Ambiguities

A language authority serves as the ultimate arbiter in resolving debates about proper language usage. This includes:

- Clarifying ambiguous grammatical rules or word meanings.
 - Setting formal rules for contentious areas of language (e.g., gender-neutral pronouns, correct spellings, or pronunciation standards).
- Providing authoritative answers in legal and academic contexts where precise language use is crucial.

6. Promotion of Clear Communication

By offering standardized language rules, a language authority ensures that:

- Official documents (e.g., legal texts, government publications) are unambiguous and easily understood.
- Everyday communication, whether written or spoken, is clear and effective , avoiding misunderstandings or confusion.

7. Supporting Minority and Endangered Languages

In multilingual societies, a language authority can play a vital role in:

- Protecting minority languages , ensuring they are not lost to dominant languages.
 - Standardizing these languages , providing resources such as dictionaries and textbooks, thus preserving linguistic diversity.

In conclusion, a language authority provides a framework for ensuring that a language is preserved, evolves in a structured manner, and remains functional for its speakers. While languages naturally change, the role of an authority is to balance innovation and tradition, ensuring that communication remains efficient, clear, and culturally rich. In the absence of such an authority, a language risks fragmenting into incompatible dialects or losing coherence, which can lead to widespread miscommunication and a diminished cultural identity.

The European Union could adopt such measures to implement a common language on the territory of the EU Member States, and a citizens' initiative would be a good omen.